

Research

An observational study of Lake Breeze over the Victoria basin in Uganda

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Abstract: The objective of this study was to explore lake and land breezes over the Lake Victoria basin based on 2 years (2019 to 2020). Hourly and daily data of wind speed and direction, precipitation, 2-meter air temperature over land, and Lake mix-layer depth obtained from Era 5 re-analysis were utilized. The method employed was based on the characteristics of the lake breeze with the elimination of the days with strong synoptic winds. According to the results, the main drivers for the breeze development at the meteorological stations were the thermal gradient between the lake and the surroundings and the low-level winds. The breezes mainly occur between 9:00 h and 15:00 h characterized by divergence over the lake and reduction in temperature and they move over land. The study calls for a look at the factors that may contribute to the formation of the breezes.

Keywords: Victoria basin, Breeze, Era5, Uganda

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1. Introduction

Lake and land breezes are thermally induced mesoscale characteristics that occur as a result of daily differential heating between land and sea/lake, creating a horizontal pressure gradient that allows cool and humid air to reach inland (Ramis et al., 1990; Naor et al., 2017). These circulations are crucial in determining the type of local weather that happens in a specific place (Azorin-Molina et al., 2009; Alexander, 2012; Leshamta, 2017) demonstrated that lake and land wind circulations have a significant impact on the location, timing, and intensity of convective initiation and storms. They also have a significant impact on tornado and thunderstorm climatology, possibly suppressing or strengthening violent thunderstorms in locations where they are more likely to occur (King et al., 2003). The circulations of lake and land breezes are very well understood and well recognized for pollutant transmission (Sills et al., 2010), therefore a better knowledge of their properties would be extremely beneficial.

One of the world's most researched mesoscale atmospheric circulations is the sea/land and land breeze circulations. That is multiple descriptive and observational studies on the features of the breeze in various locations across the world. Jansfi and Jaume, (1956); Neumann, (1951); Bitan, (1981); Druilhet et al., (1982); Lalas et al., (1983); Prezerakos, (1986); Carpenter, (1979); Mahfouf et al., (1987) and more recently Keeler and Kristovich, (2012); Wu et al., (2013); Mariani, Dehghan, and Sills (2018); Chi-Hung (2019); Jayakrishnan et al., (2021), the origins of these mesoscale circulations were considered to be geographically stable in most of these studies.

However, different scholars have made efforts trying to understand the different characteristics of the lake/land breezes for example studies by Segal et al. (1997); Xu et al. (2019); Purificação et al. (2021) examined the temperature or sensible heat flux gradients influence, other studies on the strength and direction of synoptic flow by (Estoque, 1962; Simpson et al., 1977; Arritt, 1997; Comer and McKendry, 1993; Laird et al., 2001; Wang et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019), stability (Mak and Walsh, 1976; Arritt, 1993; Crosman and Horel, 2012), size, depth and shape of the lake (Neumann and Mahrer, 1975; Physick, 1976; Segal et al., 1997); height and slope of surrounding terrain (Wexler, 1946; Estoque, 1981; Estoque and Gross, 1981; Zumpfe and Horel, 2007) and roughness length of the surrounding land (Stivari et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2017).

Though for most previous studies about Lake Victoria's lake-land breeze circulation focused on the mean diurnal cycle of winds, moisture, and precipitation, ignoring daily variability, and smoothing out small-scale details (Mukabana and Pielke, 1996; Song et al., 2004; Anyah et al., 2006; Thiery et al., 2015; Camberlin et al., 2018; Woodhams et al., 2019; Van et al., 2020; Nicholson et al., 2021; Van et al., 2021) and less has been done on the timing of the breeze circulations over the Lake Victoria. In addition, the goal to achieve accurate seasonal forecasts is very critical in the region due to the existence of complex topography and large inland water bodies (Indeje et al., 2000; Mugume et al., 2016; Ngailo et al., 2016) which are responsible for the intra-seasonal variations (Odongo and Mugume, 2019). This complexity results in mesoscale features which influence weather over Uganda including land and lake breeze. In general, this land-lake breeze process results in the lake basin region receiving some rains almost throughout the year.

The general forecasting approach must be based on the fact that breeze circulations are cyclical, and the forces are very stable (Erik and John, 2010). This allows us to use climatic studies of the breeze in a given area rather effectively. Thus, this work will focus on the observational and characterization of Lake Breeze over Lake Victoria, Uganda (East Africa). The rest of the work is organized as follows. Section 2 gives a brief description of the area of study, datasets, criteria for breeze detection, and methods employed, section 3 presents the results and lastly, section 4 discusses the findings and concludes the study.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Site Description.

The study focuses on the Uganda side of the Lake Victoria basin of East Africa (Figure 1a). Lake Victoria is the largest freshwater lake in East Africa and Africa at large shared by three countries: Uganda, Kenya, and Tanzania. It is part of depression within the East African Great Rift Valley, between two mountain ranges, generally running north-south, on both sides and one of Africa's great lakes. The lake is bounded by latitudes 0.5° N and 2.5° S and longitudes 32° E and 34° E covering an area of 69,000 km² (Semazzi, 2011), but it is also one of the shallowest; the bathymetry within the lake is asymmetrical east to west with an average depth of 45 m (Song et al., 2004). The lake has a big influence on people's social and economic life as millions of people depend on it for many resources (Enserink and Onencan, 2017).

Many people in the region rely on the lake for food, water, income, and energy (World Bank, 2015), and it has long served as a convenient method to travel between the three nations via boat transport (Ntiba, Kudoja, and Mukasa, 2001). Moreover, the lake serves as the industrial and domestic water supply for around 5 million people who live in the major cities that surround it. Lake Victoria is also a notable biodiversity reserve, home to 400 indigenous fish species. Wetlands filter silt and nutrients before they enter the lake, offer habitat for fish reproduction, and produce construction materials, fuelwood, and feed for a large rural population (Swallow et al., 2003; Noordwijk et al., 2009).

Fig 1: Location of Lake Victoria Basin N in East Africa (a). In addition, the figure shows the location and topography [m] of the study region, the Lake Victoria basin in Uganda (b).

2.2. Climatology

The climatology over Lake Victoria is due to both local (mesoscale) and large-scale (synoptic-scale) influences (Argent et al., 2015). The local (mesoscale) dynamics associated with the geography of the Rift Valley Complex and the lake itself (Anyah and Semazzi, 2014), the surrounding climate regimes, and synoptic scale features that are transient over the region all combine to create a highly complex and interesting climatology over the LVB. Characterized by a large land-lake breeze circulation system due to the lake and surrounding land (Ogwang et al., 2014), large-scale winds over the lake basin are mainly easterly monsoons most of the year, with two rainy seasons i.e., March-April-May and September-October-November. The climatology of the Lake Victoria basin is in detail explained by Anyah and Semazzi, (2014).

2.3. Data used in the study.

Researchers carrying out research in the region have resorted to using reanalysis and satellite-derived datasets due to a paucity of in-situ data in the region (Woodhams et al., 2019). Even though existing in-situ observations of the lake-land breeze circulation have been obtained from surface weather stations with fixed locations (Lumb, 1970; Datta, 1981), they are difficult to use in isolation to build a complete picture of the circulation, especially if the recording frequency is low due to a lack of upper-air observation. Thus, in this study, a reanalysis of version 5 (ERA5) (Table 1) hourly dataset obtained from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) was adopted.

ERA5 is produced using 4D-Var data assimilation and model forecasts in CY41R2 of the ECMWF Integrated Forecast System (IFS), with 137 hybrid sigma/pressure (model) levels in the vertical and the top-level at 0.01 hPa. Atmospheric data are available on these levels, and they are also interpolated to 37 pressure, 16 potential temperatures, and 1 potential vorticity level(s) by FULL-POS in the IFS.

Table 1: Description of ERA 5 data used

Data type	Gridded
Projection	Regular latitude-longitude grid
Horizontal coverage	Global
Horizontal resolution	0.1° x 0.1°; Native resolution is 9 km.

Vertical coverage	From 2 m above the surface level, to a soil depth of 289 cm.
Vertical resolution	4 levels of the ECMWF surface model: Layer 1: 0 -7cm, Layer 2: 7 -28cm, and Layer 3: 28-100 cm, Layer 4: 100-289cm Some parameters are defined at 2 m over the surface.
Temporal coverage	January 1950 to present

2.4. Criteria for Breeze Detection

Lake Breeze like the Sea breeze days has been defined using a variety of criteria. According to the literature from different Studies for example by Chen and Nunez, (1998), Giovannini et al. (2015), Lakunin et al. (2017), and Purificação et al. (2021), the lake breezes are regulated by diverse characteristics depending upon geographical location and obtained data. The first criterion for excluding days with strong synoptic variability is used for breeze days. The second condition is based on the requirement for the creation of breeze days, which is that there must be a temperature differential between the water and the land. Other proposed conditions were, the presence of an upper return flow and the occurrence to be categorized as a breeze day, the onshore component of the surface wind must surpass the onshore component of the free-stream wind. In this study, the criteria adopted consist of six filters, developed following (Lyons and Olsson, 1972; Banfield, 1991).

Fig 2: Flow diagram showing the different filters used in the technique.

- I. 500-hPa geostrophic wind direction changes $< 90^\circ$ during a 24-h period (from 1300LT of the previous day until 1300 LT of present-day),
- II. 500-hPa geostrophic wind speed changes $< 6 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ during a 12-h period (from 0100LT until 1300 LT of the present day).
- III. 500-hPa geostrophic wind speed $< 11 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ until 1300 LT.
- IV. The change in the 2-meter temperature of the present day at a land station (T_x), and surface temperature at a station over the water (T_w), must fulfill the relationship $T_x - T_w > 3^\circ\text{C}$, during the previous 24-h period,
- V. Surface wind direction changes at a land station $> 30^\circ$ from 1hr after sunrise until 6hr before sunset,
- VI. For days with daily precipitation events greater than 0.5 mm must be discarded

2.5. Method Assumptions.

The creation of the selection procedure relies on several assumptions. The rapid shift in wind direction at the 10 m level might be related to the commencement of a lake breeze, according to one theory. The approach is also designed to accommodate a variety of Lake Breeze features, such as Lake Breeze veering and variable onset periods. The pulsing quality of the lake breeze, which normally lasts 10 to 20 minutes, is a distinguishing aspect that should not be disregarded. These factors rarely influence the lake breeze criteria proposed here, i.e., based on hourly averages of wind direction. The strategy relies on the formation of a lake wind during the day, namely 1 hour after sunrise and 1 hour before sunset. The necessity for consistent wind direction conditions for 5 hours after commencement is added to this.

It is possible that lake breezes, which develop in the very late afternoon, will be rejected in the selection process. Because the criterion is rather sharply defined, some lake breeze days will not pass through the filters and therefore the method will underestimate the lake breeze frequency. Nevertheless, the rather small data set that will have passed all six filters, will provide ideal conditions for process studies on Lake Breeze development over the LVB.

3. Results

3.1. Thermal Gradient between Lake and Land

The thermal contrast between the reservoir and adjacent land is the crucial factor for the development of lake and land breezes (Bajamgnigni and Steyn, 2012). To examine the thermal contrast between land and the lake, three onshore stations and three within the lake corresponding to the onshore stations were considered. Figure 3 (a-c) illustrates the differences between air temperature in onshore stations and Lake mix-layer temperature which is the temperature of the uppermost layer of inland water bodies (lakes, reservoirs, and rivers) or coastal waters) that is well mixed. For Jinja and Kamenyamigo stations, the temperature difference exhibits some seasonality, in general, during wet seasons the average air temperature differences between shores and reservoir are positive unlike for the Entebbe-Buku (3b) station where temperature differences are negative for the entire study period.

Fig 3: Temperature Deference Between Temperature of air at 2m above the surface of land and The temperature of the upper most layer of inland water bodies (Lake mix-layer temperature) at different stations, (a) Jinja, (b) Entebbe-buku, and (c) Kamenyamigo.

3.2. Number of breeze days

The monthly frequencies of the lake-breeze occurrence on the three lake shores (Jinja, Entebbe-Buku and Kamenyamigo) are presented in Figure 4. The frequency is defined as the number of days passed the criteria for the lake breeze identification for a given month. Over Jinja, the highest breeze days between 22 – 26 days occur during August and September while March-May depicts the lowest number of breeze days of less than 3 days. Entebbe experiences the most breezy days (19 – 25) during February, August and September whereas no low breezes occur during April and November and May shows no breeze over the region. On contrary, Kamenyamigo experiences breeze days almost throughout the year with the highest (20 – 26) occurring during January and June and November depicting the lowest of 6 days. Generally, more breeze days are occurring in the dry seasons (JJA and DJF) than in wet seasons (MAM and SON).

Fig 4: Distribution of lake-breeze days by month for the study period at each station, (a) Jinja station, (b) Entebbe Buku station, and (c) Kamenyamigo station.

Further analysis of the diurnal cycle of the occurrence of the breezes was done (Figure 5), each onset hour of the occurrence of the breeze was considered as the time when it occurred and it is evident that at all the stations considered, the maximum number of breezes occur between 9:00 h and 13:00 h. It was also noted that beyond 15:00 h there are no breezes occurrences at Jinja and Entebbe stations but there are breezes that occurred in Kamenyamigo beyond 3 pm. About the diurnal cycle of temperature more inversion occurred in the same hours when more breezes occurred for all the stations (Figure 6).

Fig 5: Diurnal cycle breezes for the study period at Kamenyamigo (a), Jinja (b) and Entebbe-buku (c) stations.

Fig 6: Mean Diurnal cycle of the 2m temperature for the study period.

3.3. Wind roses per station for the study period

The wind roses for the whole period are presented in Figure 7 for Kamenyamigo (a), Entebbe-Buku (b), and Jinja (c), stations. The predominance of stronger winds lies between southwest, west, and Northwest components, with almost 14% in Jinja and Entebbe-Buku stations and 28% in Kamenyamigo. In Kamenyamigo, the highest frequency was observed in the west, in Entebbe-Buku it was in the west-north-west, and in Jinja, it was in North-west.

Fig 7: Wind roses (left) and wind speed frequencies per direction (right) for the full period in Jinja (a), Entebbe-Buku (b), Kamenyamigo (c) stations

3.4. Spatiotemporal Characteristics of the breeze.

In this section, two typical cases, which occurred on 4 June 2019 and 7 February 2020, are presented to demonstrate an application of the method defined in this study for the identification of the occurrence of a lake breeze. Then the life cycle of the breeze circulation is discussed to highlight the spatiotemporal evolution of the observed breezes.

A Case study 4th/6/2019

The On June 4th, 2019, – Basin experienced the greatest land breeze duration (h) and a breeze occurrence was observed at all three stations. Wind roses were plotted for this day and multiple wind directions were observed (Figure 8). The change in wind direction offshore near the surface implies divergence over the lake. This is also evident that the lake was dominated by the divergence of wind (Figure 9). From the wind rose diagram, the dominant wind components at the different stations were also observed to be in the direction away from the Lake. On this day, no strong component of wind was observed over the lake but rather it blew in different directions from the lake due to the divergence over the lake.

Fig 8: Wind rose for the full day and during land breeze occurrences for all the stations; Jinja (a), Emtebbe-buku (b), and Kamenyamigo (c)

The lake breeze formed at 9:00 UTC and traversed to the north with an average horizontal speed of 1.6ms⁻¹, a vertical wind speed component of about 6 ms⁻¹ (Figure 9), and an average decrease in temperature of about 1.80c. The Height-latitude cross-section of wind speed was plotted to examine the vertical variations in the wind speed, where stronger winds are observed at lower levels over the lake between 0.5o S and 3.0o S and it reduces towards inland (Figure 10).

Fig 9: Shows surface divergence over Lake Victoria on the breeze day.

Fig 10: Height-latitude cross-section of wind speed over the basin on 4th/6/2019

7th/01/2020

Unlike the case study of 2019, the lake breeze of 7th/01/2020 was observed only on two weather stations of Entebbe-Buku and Jinja stations. There exhibited a larger area of divergence over the lake but mainly observed (the change in wind directions) at the stations where the breeze occurred (Figure 11). This was mainly at two stations of Entebbe-Buku and Jinja stations.

Fig 11: Wind rose for the full day and during land breeze occurrences for all the stations; Jinja (a), Entebbe-buku (b), and Kamenyamigo (c).

Throughout the hours of the lake breeze occurrence, a strong component of westerly winds was observed more so when the breeze is fully developed (Figure 12). There is a convergence that is seen to occur at a given distance from the lake. From the height-latitude cross-section, stronger winds are observed at 1.50S and 2.50S. A strong wind component is also observed at 700Mb more so in the northern part of the lake (Figure 13).

Fig 12: Shows divergence over Lake Victoria on the breeze day

Fig 13: Height-latitude cross-section of wind speed over the basin on 7th/2/2020

4. Discussion

The objective of the present study was to explore the lake and land breezes over the Lake Victoria basin. The study was based on 2 years (2019 to 2020) and utilized hourly and daily data of wind speed and direction, precipitation, 2-meter air temperature over land, and Lake mix-layer depth.

The results show that the thermal gradient established between the shores and the lake and low wind speed are the main triggers for the development of lake and land breezes which agrees with the findings of Purificação et al., (2021). The thermal gradient analysis was twofold: the air temperature difference between the shores and the lake and the

difference between the 2-meter air temperature on the shores and the lake mix layer temperature, which is the temperature of the uppermost layer of inland water bodies (lakes, reservoirs, rivers, and coastal waters) that is well mixed and has a nearly constant temperature with depth.

There are more positive temperature gradients at the Jinja stations and more negative gradients at the Entebbe-Buku and Kamenyamigo stations. This means that more land breezes occur at Jinja station than at the Entebbe-Buku and Kamenyamigo stations. The observed breezes have mainly been reported to occur between 9:00 and 15:00 h with onset just after sunrise, which supports findings of Bajamgnigni et al., (2013).

The study demonstrated the monthly distribution of breeze days for the study period, and it was evident that there are more breeze days in the dry months (seasons) of the year. This is because it's the time when the study region experiences weak synoptic winds according to Ngoma et al. (2021) and this was noted by Mutai et al. (2012) and Defzuli and Nicholson. (2013), those strong westerlies are favored by a steep eastward.

5. Conclusion

From the two case studies, the breezes are triggered by temperature gradients between the lake and land which lead to the divergence over the lake, which is also associated with nocturnal low-level convergence. The variations in the wind directions were attributed to the low-level divergence over the lake.

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